

Qualitative Study on Perception of First Year M.B.B.S. Students toward Orientation Program and Foundation Course at Entry Level**Bhavna Gupta¹, Chhaya Batham², Shilpa Waghmare³, Pratibha Verma⁴**¹Associate Professor Department of Physiology LN Medical College Bhopal²Assistant Professor Department of Physiology Gandhi Medical College Bhopal³Assistant Professor Department of Physiology NSCB Medical College, Jabalpur⁴Assistant Professor Department of Physiology Gandhi Medical College Bhopal

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Abstract:

Orientation and foundation program for MBBS students at the entry level, as suggested by the MCI, helps reduce students anxiety and boosts their confidence. It facilitates their smooth transition from high school to an undergraduatemedical course. The enthusiastic participation of newly admitted students in various sessions during the program and their feedback was very encouraging. The feedback undoubtedly indicated that students were very happy and satisfied with the program. Similar results were obtained by various previous studies. A structured foundation course, such as ours, can help alleviate students worries, and help them cope with forthcoming professional demands.

Keywords: Curriculum Reforms, Graduate Medical Regulations, Foundation Program, Curriculum Implementation Support Program.

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Introduction

Medical Education in India is being revolutionized with the introduction of “Competency- based undergraduate curriculum” for the Indian Medical Graduate (IMG). [1] It marks a significant shift from the teacher centred learning to student centred learning, which stresses the practicalities, skills development, medical ethics, and better doctor-patient relationship. The newly revised curriculum insists on the foundation course of one month duration at the beginning of the MBBS program with an objective to sensitize the fresh medical students with the required knowledge and skills that will assist them in acclimatizing and making them familiar to the new professional environment. As envisaged by the Medical Council of India (MCI), an IMG should have attributes like Clinician, Lifelong Learner, Leader, Communicator, and Professional. The foundation course helps the students to get an overview of the MBBS curriculum and learn medicine effectively to achieve the required attributes. [2]

NEET does not consider extracurricular abilities of these students. Furthermore, students belonging to diverse sociocultural, religious, economic, and geographic backgrounds come together at a medical college to pursue their MBBS. Such teenage students have varying psychological framework and may find it difficult to adapt to the new academic environment. As medicine is a challenging profession that demands the study of a large volume

of knowledge, acquisition of novel clinical skills, self-directed learning, ethical behavior, and professional attitudes, the MCI has suggested conducting a foundation course of 2 months for the first-year MBBS students with the aim of producing competent Indian Medical Graduates. In India, students enter medical profession at the age of 17-19 years. At such a tender age, this cohort of students has dissimilar psychological characteristics such as fear of ragging, feeling of homesickness, peer pressure, parental pressures, language problems, and adjustments to hostel life and food. They come from different sociocultural backgrounds and have diverse expectations from the medical profession. On top of these, they are burdened with various expectations from family and society. In such a psychological state, they are expected to understand and appreciate the medical subjects. [3]

The overall program was coordinated by the Dean of college. To begin with, Medical Education Unit (MEU) organized the “Curriculum Implementation and Support Program (CISP)” for the faculty members of pre-clinical department for planning, implementing, and evaluating the new curriculum. The focus of the CISP was on four curricular strategies: foundation course, early clinical exposure, integrated teaching, and skills training. Later, all pre-clinical department faculty played a key role in

outlining the schedule and planning for the foundation course. This was in alignment with the MCI guidelines. The schedule was approved by the Curriculum Committee and displayed it on the college website. Afterwards, a couple of meetings were organized to finalize the resource persons, allocating the sessions, framing the session objectives, and discussion on the sessions planned by the resource persons. [4] The faculty were encouraged to use various teaching learning methods such as lectures, interactive sessions, role plays, small group discussions, interviews, reflective writing, presentations, and debate to meet the session objectives and thereby program goals. The faculty were instructed to plan their session and discuss with the dean the feasibility and resources required for their respective session. For selected topics like soft skills, children with special needs and Yoga, external resource persons were invited to lead the sessions. In collaboration with the Engineering College faculty, the planning of the content to be delivered regarding language and computer skills was carried out.

Various colleges all over the country have developed and implemented this course to acclimatize the students to the new environment as per their resources. This is to be further supplemented by language and Computer skills. These components are multifaceted and require resource faculty.

Materials and Methods

The structural framework of support includes the Medical Education Unit (MEU) of the institutions and the Nodal and Regional Centers of the MCI. To these, the MCI has added the governance oversight of the curriculum in the form of the Curriculum Committee (CC) at the institutional level. The members of CC have the responsibility of training faculty of their respective colleges. The educators are required to impart transformative learning to create leaders in healthcare delivery system for the community. The thrust in the new Regulations is continuation and evolution of thought in medical education making it more learner-centric, patient-centric, gender-sensitive, outcome oriented and environment appropriate. The training is intense and demands greater commitment, resilience, and lifelong learning. The revised curriculum was implemented by all medical colleges under the ambit of MCI in August 2019. The roll out of the overall curricular reforms will be progressive over the duration of the MBBS course.

It was a cross-sectional study. Orientation program and foundation course were organized by the MEU,

L.N. Medical College and J.K. Hospital for the incoming first-year MBBS students of 2021-2022 batch. Prior approval for the study was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee of L.N. Medical College. 180 students voluntarily participated in this three-day long program held from September 28, 2021, to October 1, 2022, and gave written informed consent for the same. MEU faculty facilitated all the sessions and motivated students to participate actively. Students' feedback was obtained by a pre-designed and pre-validated questionnaire on a five-point Likert scale.

The major components of the course contain six modules like; Orientation, Skills, Community orientation, Professionalism & ethics, Enhancement of language, computer skills, Sports, and Extracurricular activities. Each module has specific topic wise hour distribution with special hours allotted to sports and extracurricular activities. Orientation program is considered valuable in lowering the anxiety of new workplace, and can benefit both faculty and the new entrants from various disciplines. Many of these identified areas top needed to be followed up by outcome-based sessions.

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Primary Objectives:

1. To assess students' feedback on all topics of all the modules of the Foundation course namely 1) Orientation module, 2) Skills module, 3) Community Orientation module, 4) Professional Development and Ethics module, 5) Language and Computer Skills, & 6) Sports and Extracurricular activities.
2. To get suggestions for improvement of the course.

Secondary Objectives:

1. To assess whether the course along with year-long support is achieving its purpose.
2. Improving the subsequent course for upcoming batch based on suggestions given by the students.
3. Restructuring of the teaching methodology if required.

Observation Chart

Table 1: Students Feedback on Orientation Program

Feedback	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Orientation program					
Interesting	38	36	20	3	0
Nicely organized	39	42	13	0	1
Satisfied	27	45	23	1	0
Enjoyed	38	41	16	1	0
Impressive	61	25	9	1	0
Average	78		16	4	

Table 2: Students Feedback on Foundation Course

Feedback	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Foundation program	35	54	11	1	0
Useful	39	44	13	4	1
Informative	27	51	18	4	1
Effective	60	36	4	0	0
Helpful to get oriented with MBBS	54	40	4	1	1
Helpful in building up confidence	88		10	2	
Average					

Results

Of 112 students, 107 students responded with the feedback, whereas 5 students did not respond. Feedback of students on orientation program, 74% (n=82) students found the program interesting, whereas 81% (m=91) students found the program nicely organized. 72% (m = 80) students were satisfied with the orientation program. 79% (n = BB) students said that they enjoyed the program and 86% (n=96) students found the program impressive. Overall, 78% students responded favorably, 16% students responded neutral while 4% students responded unfavorably for the program.

As far as feedback of students on foundation course. All the 112 students responded with the feedback. 89% (n = 99) students found the program useful, whereas 83% (n = 93) students found it informative. 78% (n=87) students said that the course was effective. 96% (n = 107) students said that the program was helpful in getting oriented to the MBBS course while 94% (n = 105) students said that it helped boost their confidence. Overall, 88% students responded favorably, 10% students responded neutral while 2% students responded unfavorably for the program.

Major themes that emerged from students' open-ended responses regarding the entire program:

- It was a unique and lifelong memorable experience for me
- All my doubts were addressed in the program
- The program relieved my anxiety
- I am very happy to find helpful and supportive staff
- I am excited about the mentorship program

- I enjoyed company of seniors
- I am satisfied with the program
- I suggest that cultural programs may be added to this program
- I had some difficulty understanding in English and wish for more usage of local languages
- I found it a very long and exhaustive program

Statistical Analysis:

All statistical analysis was done by the help of appropriate statistical software. Validity of the questionnaire will be assessed by Cronbach's alpha score ≥ 0.7 . For quantitative data frequency distribution, measures of central tendency, dispersion, and graphical representation were applied. For qualitative data frequency distribution, percentage and various diagrammatic representations were applied. A summative approach to the qualitative content analysis was done to identify certain themes from the text data and infer meaning for the force field analysis obtained from the faculty. Considering the high rating for most of the sessions, we arbitrarily considered values above 75% to reflect good consensus and below 75% to reflect poor consensus. Consensus measure expressed in percentage was obtained for each item. The quantitative data were analyzed using open Epi info version 7.0. Appropriate statistical test like Paired t test were applied. Value of p less than 0.05 will be considered as significant. The analysis was done using the SSPS 24.0 statistical software.

Discussion

In our study we found the rating of the foundation course given by the students in the feedback form to

be very encouraging. Most of the students not only gained knowledge and improved their skills, but the foundation course also helped them in boosting their confidence level. As the foundation course is a new initiative taken by the MCI for overall betterment of medical (professional) education in India, we suggest that this type of feedback about the program will also help in generating new innovative ways and ideas of teaching which will be beneficial not only for the students but the medical fraternity as a whole and ultimately health of our society and country. [6]

Perspectives of students when obtained provide richer experiences and in-depth understanding of issues at hand than quantitative data alone. We also made efforts to gather perspectives of students through few open-ended questions where the students quoted that, the Foundation Program highlights benefits, is a valuable vehicle for increasing students' overall confidence. The program benefits as perceived by the students included; helping them to gain clarity on their future roles as medical professional/doctor as envisaged by MCI, orienting them to medical ethics and professionalism, enhancing their time and stress management skills, enhancing their communication, language, computer and learning skills. [7]

Since MCI had made one-month foundation course mandatory in all medical colleges of India, the foundation course organized in our medical college would provide an idea for other medical colleges about the planning, implementation, and evaluation process. The course can be followed as per the MCI guidelines in other colleges with contextual modifications as per their circumstances keeping in mind that this period is employed effectively by the students to be acclimatized with the new professional atmosphere. The present evaluation gave an idea of the advantages as well as barriers towards the implementation and the evaluation of foundation course. This will help us to improve the next foundation course for medical undergraduates. This will, in turn, help us to organize the forthcoming foundation course in an effective way. More follow-up evaluation is required to check the achievements of desired goals of the program. However, the limitation of the present evaluation should be kept in mind. As it was an evaluation study, the findings are specific to context. We measured the lower outcome of the framework and in future it would be interesting to measure the effect of this program on the students' behavior at workplace as a professional in the future.

However, there are challenges to overcome viz; optimum resources in terms of infrastructure for sports, audiovisual aids, and others. Inclusion of in-depth qualitative feedback from faculty and students would yield better insight into scaling of the program. "The Foundation Course enables the First-year students to acquire the basic knowledge and skills required for all the subsequent phases in

MBBS course and later their medical practice and career. Similar feedback responses report high level of satisfaction on part of students enabling them to cope with the vast body of knowledge and skills required in the dynamic and rapidly changing healthcare system.

Conclusion

The enthusiasm, hard work and integrated effort by the faculty members who participated in the program were extremely important for the success of this course. It is learnt that the Foundation program highlights benefits, is a valuable vehicle for increasing students' overall confidence. There are challenges involved in operationalization viz; it requires more time and effort from faculty, at least in the initial phases of program development.

Declarations:

Funding: None **Conflicts of interest/Competing interests:** None **Availability of data and material:** Department of Physiology LN Medical College Bhopal **Code availability:** Not applicable **Consent to participate:** Consent taken **Ethical Consideration:** There are no ethical conflicts related to this study. **Consent for publication:** Consent taken

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